

Hydrogen bond interaction study of methanol in non-polar solute : A theoretical dielectric approach

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Abstract : The dielectric permittivity of methanol in chlorobenzene and 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures for various concentration and temperatures have been studied using hydrogen bonded model suggested by Luzar. Luzar has proposed a more realistic hydrogen bonded model, to determine the correlation factor g_1 and g_2 from single value of the dielectric constant. The interaction of the chloro group molecules with methanol as hydrogen bonded liquid is discussed.

Keywords : Dielectric permittivity, Kirkwood correlation factor.

Introduction

Dielectric study provides information about charge distribution in a molecular system. In a molecule there exist a distribution of charge so that the centers of positive and negative charges do not coincide. Even in absence of external field, molecules that possess asymmetry in their distribution of positive and negative charge are called polar molecules. Such molecules have a permanent electric dipole moment (μ). In the absence of external field, if the center of negative and positive charge coincides the molecule is said to be in the neutral state. These types of molecules are called non-polar. Methanol is a polar hydrogen bonded primary alcohol and is widely used as an industrial solvent.

Extensive experimental dielectric studies have been carried out on methanol in order to investigate the hydrogen bond structure and intermolecular rotation in the liquids¹. The theoretical approach and computer simulation study were reported to understand the relaxation behavior and hydrogen bonding in alcohols². The calculation

of the theoretical dielectric constant using Kirkwood correlation factor provides more precise theoretical model for the mixture. Luzar³ has already suggested theoretical model for a hydrogen bonded mixture. The correlation factors were computed in the mean field approximation. The model has been successfully applied to dimethylsulphoxide-water mixture. A comparison is also made between the values of dielectric parameters obtained by the hydrogen bonded model and those measured experimentally by the Time Domain Reflectometry technique (TDR).

Experimental

Materials :

Methanol (MeOH), chlorobenzene (CB) and 1,2-dichloroethane (DE) were obtained commercially and used without purification. Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) techniques were used to determine permittivity spectra in the frequency range 10 MHz to 20 GHz⁴. The Hewlett Packard HP54750A sampling oscilloscope with HP54754A TDR plug in modules has been used to study the complex

permittivity spectra. Details of the experimental procedure of the Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) have already been reported⁴.

Results and discussion

The relation between dielectric constant and dipole moment can be given by the Kirkwood equation as follows.

$$\frac{4\pi Nd}{9kTM} g\mu^2 = \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)(2\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_\infty)}{\epsilon_0(\epsilon_\infty + 2)} \quad (1)$$

where N is the Avogadro's number, d is the density of the liquid, μ is the dipole moment of the liquid, ϵ_0 is the static dielectric constant, ϵ_∞ is the dielectric constant at high frequency and kT has the usual meaning. The correlation factor provides the following information's in the liquids as follows.

- (i) $g = 1$ indicates that there is no interaction between the molecules in liquid. The system may be considered like non-polar.
- (ii) $g > 1$ indicates parallel alignment of dipoles in multimers.

Luzar introduced the cross correlation terms to determine correlation factor g_1 and g_2 from a single static dielectric permittivity, using Kirkwood-Frohlich equation. The correlation factor g_1 and g_2 were computed in the mean field approximation as follows.

$$g_1 = 1 + Z_{11} \overline{\cos \phi_{11}} + Z_{12} \overline{\cos \phi_{12}} \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} \quad (2)$$

$$g_2 = 1 + Z_{21} \overline{\cos \phi_{21}} \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} \quad (3)$$

where, $Z_{11} = 2 \langle n_{HB}^{11} \rangle$; $Z_{12} = \langle n_{HB}^{12} \rangle$; $Z_{21} = \frac{\langle n_{HB}^{12} \rangle X_1}{(1 - X_1)}$

ϕ_{11} , ϕ_{12} and ϕ_{21} denotes the angle between neighboring dipoles of solvent-solvent, solvent-solute and solute-solvent molecules. Z_{11} , Z_{21} and Z_{12} are the average number of particles forming the hydrogen bond with solvent-solvent, solute-solvent and solvent-solute molecules pair, respectively.

The average numbers of hydrogen bonds per solvent molecules depend on the number densities of hydrogen bonding pair between solvent and solute molecule and

are determined according to the following equation.

$$\langle n_{HB}^{11} \rangle = n_{11} \omega_{11} / n_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\langle n_{HB}^{12} \rangle = n_{12} \omega_{12} / n_1 \quad (5)$$

where

$$\omega_{11} = \frac{1}{(1 + \alpha_{11} e^{-\beta E_{11}})} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\omega_{12} = \frac{1}{(1 + \alpha_{12} e^{-\beta E_{12}})} \quad (7)$$

are the probabilities of bond formation between solvent and solute molecules. The value of $\beta = 1/kT$ and α_{11} and α_{12} are the ratio of the two sub volumes of the phase space related to the non hydrogen bonded and hydrogen bonded pairs. The different molecular parameters required in the hydrogen bonded model are given in Table 1. The model gives a good qualitative account of the dielectric

Table 1. Molecular parameters used in computation of the static dielectric constant

Molecular parameters	Symbol	
Dipole moment of methanol in Debye	(μ_1^0)	2.10
Dipole moment of chlorobenzene in Debye	(μ_2^0)	2.16
Dipole moment of 1,2-dichloroethane in Debye	(μ_2^0)	2.67
Polarizability for methanol in \AA^3	(α_1)	3.00
Polarizability for solute in \AA^3	(α_2)	2.59
Binding energy for methanol-methanol ^a	(E_{11})	-13.00
Binding energy for methanol-solute	(E_{12})	-14.00
Statistical volume ratio for methanol-methanol	(α_{11})	28
Statistical volume ratio for methanol-solute	(α_{12})	40
Number of hydrogen bond	(m)	3

^aUnits : kJ mol⁻¹.

constant of the binary mixtures along with the experimental values determined from Time Domain Reflectometry technique (TDR) in our laboratory. It can be seen from Tables 2 and 3 that the theoretical values are in general smaller than the corresponding experimental values.

The Kirkwood correlation factors g_1 and g_2 for methanol-CB and methanol-DE were calculated using eqs. (2) and (3) and the same are given in Tables 4 and 5. It is well known that methanol is a polar and protic solvent with a structure which is determined to a great extent by hydrogen bonding between molecules. The Kirkwood correlation for methanol solvent is generally higher than one.

Note

Table 2. Comparison of experimental values of static dielectric constant with theoretical values obtained from Luzar model

Mole fraction of methanol in chlorobenzene	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C		45 °C	
	Expt. ^a	Theor. ^b						
	0.00	5.94	5.70	5.54	5.54	5.51	5.39	5.33
0.10	7.07	8.02	7.01	7.75	6.98	7.49	6.72	7.25
0.20	9.69	10.46	10.35	10.07	9.77	9.70	9.69	9.36
0.30	12.22	13.02	14.23	12.51	13.19	12.03	12.22	11.58
0.60	16.84	21.54	19.54	20.64	18.60	19.78	16.84	18.96
0.70	21.98	24.69	23.60	23.64	21.78	22.64	20.13	21.69
0.80	28.06	28.00	28.36	26.80	26.59	25.66	25.06	24.57
0.90	30.91	31.50	31.22	30.14	28.89	28.84	27.17	27.61
1.00	35.51	35.20	34.64	33.66	32.62	32.20	30.91	31.73

Table 3. Comparison of experimental values of static dielectric constant with theoretical values obtained from Luzar model

Mole fraction of methanol in 1,2-dichloroethane	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C		45 °C	
	Expt. ^a	Theor. ^b						
	0.00	10.58	10.77	10.43	10.44	10.10	10.12	9.82
0.10	13.80	13.10	12.91	12.65	12.54	12.22	12.06	11.82
0.20	15.66	15.45	14.63	14.88	14.44	14.33	13.67	13.82
0.30	19.09	17.79	17.65	17.10	17.08	16.45	16.49	15.84
0.50	23.27	22.56	21.65	21.64	21.11	20.76	20.42	19.93
0.60	26.78	24.99	24.92	23.95	24.21	22.96	23.44	22.03
0.80	30.60	29.99	28.82	28.71	27.88	27.48	26.81	26.33
0.90	32.40	32.56	31.11	31.16	29.76	29.81	28.84	28.55
1.00	36.37	35.20	33.69	33.66	32.55	32.20	31.67	30.82

Table 4. The values g_1 and g_2 at different temperatures

Mole fraction of methanol in chlorobenzene	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C		45 °C	
	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2
	0.00	-	1.00	-	1.00	-	1.00	-
0.10	1.69	1.13	1.68	1.13	1.67	1.13	1.65	1.12
0.20	1.78	1.25	1.76	1.25	1.74	1.24	1.72	1.23
0.30	1.85	1.36	1.83	1.35	1.81	1.34	1.79	1.33
0.60	2.02	1.62	2.00	1.61	1.97	1.59	1.95	1.57
0.70	2.07	1.69	2.04	1.67	2.02	1.66	1.99	1.64
0.80	2.11	1.75	2.09	1.74	2.06	1.72	2.03	1.70
0.90	2.15	1.81	2.12	1.79	2.10	1.78	2.07	1.76
1.00	2.19	-	2.16	-	2.13	-	2.11	-

Table 5. The values g_1 and g_2 at different temperatures

Mole fraction of methanol in 1,2-dichloroethane	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C		45 °C	
	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2	g_1	g_2
0.00	-	1.00	-	1.00	-	1.00	-	1.00
0.10	1.81	1.09	1.79	1.09	1.78	1.09	1.76	1.08
0.20	1.86	1.18	1.84	1.17	1.82	1.18	1.80	1.16
0.30	1.91	1.25	1.89	1.25	1.87	1.24	1.85	1.24
0.60	2.00	1.40	1.98	1.39	1.96	1.38	1.93	1.37
0.70	2.04	1.47	2.02	1.46	2.00	1.45	1.97	1.43
0.80	2.12	1.59	2.09	1.58	2.07	1.56	2.04	1.55
0.90	2.15	1.65	2.13	1.64	2.10	1.62	2.08	1.60
1.00	2.19	-	2.16	-	2.13	-	2.11	-

The deviation of the Kirkwood correlation from unity is a measure of the short range intermolecular interactions and associations. When volume fraction of solvent is small, each solvent molecule is surrounded by solute molecules and forms hydrogen bonds with it. In solvent rich solution, solvent molecules may form hydrogen bonds with other molecules of solvent as well as with solute molecules as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Therefore g_1 and g_2 depend on the number densities of hydrogen bonding pairs between solvent and solute molecules, and those between solvent molecules. The solute molecules diminish the correlation parameter. In other words, solute is efficient at breaking the structure of dipole-correlating hydrogen bonds in solvents.

Conclusions :

Binary mixture of methanol-chlorobenzene and 1,2-dichloroethane over entire range of compositions have been studied by hydrogen bonded model suggested by Luzar. The Luzar theory is applied to determine the molecular parameters and correlation terms for the mixture. The calculated and experimental values of permittivity are reported. The information regarding hydrogen bonding structure behavior in methanol due to chloro group are obtained by using the theoretical model. In view of supportive comparisons with the experimental, one may conclude, that the model captures some of the essential physical features that determine dielectric properties of hydrogen bonded liquids.

Fig. 1. The average number of hydrogen bonds between methanol-methanol (n_{11} pair) and methanol-chlorobenzene (n_{12} pair) against mole fraction of methanol.

Note

Fig. 2. The average number of hydrogen bonds between methanol-methanol (n_{11} pair) and methanol-1,2-dichloroethane (n_{12} pair) against mole fraction of methanol.

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References

1. K. S. Kanse, S. D. Chavan, C. S. Mali, A. C. Kumbharkhane and S. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Phys., Sect. A*, 2006, **80**, 265; A. S. Choudhary, P. W. Khirade, R. Singh, S. N. Helambe, N. K. Narin and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Mol. Liquid*, 1999, **82**, 245; M. T. Hosamani, R. H. Fattepur, D. K. Deshpande and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1995, **91**, 625; A. C. Kumbharkhane, S. M. Puranik and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1992, **21**, 201; S. N. Ahire, A. S. Choudhary, M. P. Lokhande and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1998, **27**, 993.
2. Ryuichi Minami, Kochi Itoh, Hiroaki Takahashi and Keniti Higasi, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1980, **73**, 3396; J. A. Padro. L. Saiz and E. Guardia, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1997, **416**, 243.
3. A. Luzar, *J. Mol. Liquids*, 1990, **46**, 221.
4. V. P. Pawar, G. S. Raju and S. C. Mehrotra, *Pramana J. Phys.*, 2002, **59**, 693; P. W. Khirade, A. S. Choudhary, J. B. Shinde, S. N. Helambe and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1999, **28**, 1031; S. N. Helambe, M. P. Lokhande, A. C. Kumbharkhane and S. C. Mehrotra, *Pramana J. Phys.*, 1995, **45**, 19; A. C. Kumbharkhane, S. N. Helambe, S. Daraiswami and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **99**, 2405; S. M. Puranik, A. C. Kumbharkhane and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Microwave Power and Electromagnetic Energy*, 1991, **26**, 196; A. C. Kumbharkhane, S. M. Puranik and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, **87**, 1500; S. M. Puranik, A. C. Kumbharkhane and S. C. Mehrotra, *J. Mole. Liquid*, 1994, **59**, 173; V. P. Pawar, PhD Thesis, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad, 2001.

